

Resilience: the need for an interdisciplinary research agenda for policymaking

Tongle Si ^a, t.si@tue.nl ORCID: 0000-0001-7654-9030

Pedro Senna ^b, pedro.senna@inesctec.pt ORCID: 0000-0002-4025-5716

Jaime Bonnin Roca ^{a,*} j.bonnin.roca@tue.nl ORCID: 0000-0003-4244-0357

^a Eindhoven University of Technology, Department of Industrial Engineering & Innovation Sciences; P.O. Box 513, 5600, MB, Eindhoven, The Netherlands

^b Center for Enterprise Systems Engineering, INESC TEC Institute for Systems and Computer Engineering, Technology and Science, Porto, Portugal

*Corresponding author

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Abstract

Recent crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic and geopolitical tensions around the world have highlighted the need to incorporate resilience as a key objective of public policy. However, existing literature in resilience is highly fragmented, and cannot successfully provide an answer to key pressing policy issues. In this paper, we analyze how resilience is understood and analyzed in the sustainability, economics, and management literatures. We highlight similarities and differences in resilience studies across the three fields, and some limitations which may arise when trying to use such studies to inform policymaking. We propose a research agenda for future policy-oriented resilience studies which aims to tackle some of the gaps of current work. We argue that the ultimate goal should be to create large-scale simulation models which are able to integrate economic, environmental, and societal considerations. To reach that goal, more interdisciplinary work is needed to understand the interdependencies among systems, and to create a robust data infrastructure which can support policymaking.

Introduction

In order to reduce dependency on foreign actors, increase their preparedness against unexpected crises, and provide solutions to social and environmental challenges, governments around the world have proposed different approaches to incorporate resilience in their policies. They not only possess the capacity for large-scale resource mobilization during crisis (Kontogiannis, 2021), but also hold the institutional authority to invest in preparedness infrastructure and set regulatory frameworks (Dzigbede et al., 2020). For instance, the European Union's Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) embeds resilience as a conditional criterion for national recovery plans and long-term transformation (Zeitlin et al., 2024). The U.S. approach prioritizes emergency response infrastructure through frameworks like the National Disaster Recovery Framework (NDRF), which rely on decentralized efforts at the state and local levels (Acciarini et al., 2021; Loerzel & Dillard, 2021). China has institutionalized resilience under its Five-Year Plans, in ways which are heavily tied to macroeconomic environmental and technological assessments, while comparatively neglecting social and organizational dimensions (Zhang et al., 2024). Overall, these frameworks shape firm behavior under uncertainty and position governments as potential orchestrators of inter-firm coordination and industrial networks (Amaral et al., 2023).

From an academic perspective, the interest for designing resilient systems has permeated a wide array of disciplines, from healthcare to supply chain management. In fact, a quick search reveals broad scholarly communities engaging with variants of resilience, including 'resilience thinking' (Rockström et al., 2023), 'community resilience' (Liu et al., 2022), 'regional economic resilience' (Wang & Wei, 2021), 'supply chain resilience' (Ivanov, 2024), or 'firm resilience' (Iftikhar et al., 2021). Overall, resilience has become a common term in the policy discourse (Gupta & Gupta, 2022). Researchers across fields agree that achieving resilience requires policies which combine both proactive and reactive components – emphasizing not only the capacity to anticipate and prepare for disruptions, but also the ability to respond to them (Faruquee et al., 2024; Sacco et al., 2023).

At the same time, as the use of the word resilience has become more popular, the theories scholars have developed to explain how to achieve resilience have also become more fragmented, and are currently quite far from its original meaning in ecology and environmental sciences. Some scholars have argued that resilience could act as a unifying concept between disciplines (Reed et al., 2024; Thorén, 2014). Conversely, bibliometric analyses suggest that, while the word resilience may have become a boundary object, academic communities largely remain siloed, citing within their own fields and using discipline-specific methods and tools (Baggio et al., 2015; Castillo, 2022; Hillmann, 2021). This fragmentation hinders the translation of academic results into actionable insights for policymakers.

This paper seeks to reconcile the different literature streams on resilience, with the aim of improving resilience-oriented policymaking. We explain how the concept of resilience is used in three different bodies of literature which are relevant for policymaking: economics, sustainability, and management studies. For each field, we explain the main objectives, and theoretical constructs. We identify points of convergence and tension across these streams and, building on this synthesis, propose an interdisciplinary research agenda designed to bridge conceptual divides and better inform policy decisions.

Resilience from an economics perspective

Economics scholarship focuses primarily on market mechanisms and resource allocation, rather than broader normative goals like environmental or social outcomes. Under this lens, the purpose of policy after an external shock is to be able to return to an equilibrium state, where the economic system can return to pre-shock levels of growth and efficiency (Di Pietro et al., 2021). This focus can lead to

tensions, as policies enhancing short-term recovery—such as bailouts or monetary stimulus—may prioritize rapid stabilization over investments in structural flexibility, potentially entrenching future vulnerabilities (Reinhart & Rogoff, 2009).

Economic resilience has a macroeconomic and a microeconomic component. For macroeconomic scholars, a shock can cause both losses of assets and losses of output, due to business interruptions, changes in risk attitudes, or bullwhip effects after a disruption (Hallegatte, 2014). In this sense, empirical research shows that resilience is highly dependent on the flexibility in the labor market, and existing levels of public and private debt (Jollès et al., 2023). The microeconomic perspective assesses how losses are distributed across households and small businesses, and how crises affect the provision of basic needs such as food, fresh water, or electricity (Giwa-Daramola & James, 2023; Graveline & Grémont, 2017). Furthermore, other scholars have looked at how access to financing may affect preparedness against a shock (Marincioni et al., 2013; Rajan & Ramcharan, 2023).

In recent years, some economists have moved away from equilibrium-based paradigm and adopted evolutionary views of resilience (Martin & Sunley, 2020; Tóth et al., 2022). From this evolutionary perspective, resilience involves structural adaptation – regions or economies may alter their composition in anticipation, or response, to repeated shocks. This has given rise to a distinction between inherent resilience, which is the capacity to absorb a shock without fundamental change, and adaptive resilience, the ability to reorganize and recover dynamically over time, for instance by reorganizing the industrial structure of a region (Rocchetta & Mina, 2019; Sun et al., 2025).

Inherent resilience largely depends on the pre-existing, structural attributes of an economy – such as industrial diversification, robust financial systems, and institutional stability – that can absorb stress passively. For instance, economies with low debt levels and a well-capitalized banking sector can withstand a sudden capital flight (Barbera et al., 2017). Inherent resilience is built slowly over time through policies like fiscal discipline or trade and industry diversification (Kharrazi et al., 2017; Landman et al., 2023). In contrast, adaptive resilience is the dynamic capacity to adjust and innovate in response to disruptions, and emphasizes policy agility and innovation. It requires high-quality data, administrative flexibility, and institutional capacity to implement responsive measures. Effective long-term resilience hinges on the interplay between these two dimensions. Germany, for instance, benefited from its diversified exports (inherent resilience) during the COVID-19 pandemic, but the success of its furlough schemes reflected an adaptive policy response (Baldwin & Mauro, 2020; Müller et al., 2022).

An advantage of the economic approach is the availability of a large number of indicators which allow researchers to conduct econometric analyses and perform large-scale comparisons across countries or regions (Briguglio, 2016; OECD, 2015; Wang & Wei, 2021). Global shocks, though rare, can serve as natural experiments, allowing researchers to investigate causal relationships between policies and outcomes (Arita et al., 2022; Cao & Tao, 2023). However, this presents a limitation: economic indicators primarily assess past performance and may offer limited predictive insight. For instance, global pandemic preparedness indices failed to anticipate actual country performance during COVID-19 (Abbey et al., 2020).

Resilience from a sustainability perspective

Unlike traditional economic resilience, which often emphasizes recovery to a pre-shock state (e.g., GDP growth or employment levels) and to maintain the core function (Sutton & Arku, 2022), the sustainability perspective frames resilience as a dynamic process that aligns with ecological limits and social equity. In the sustainability context, "bouncing forward" requires the transformation of the current socioeconomic system into a state that enhances also environmental and social sustainability, which usually require more substantive measures than adaptation processes in the economics

literature, and may require a shift in the core function of the economic system (Folke et al., 2010; Reyers et al., 2022). From this perspective, a resilient system might take advantage of a shock in oil prices to shift from fossil fuel dependency to renewable energy post-crisis, rather than restoring preexisting infrastructure (Nchofoung, 2024). This principle can be applied at multiple levels, from small communities (Magis, 2010), to larger regions (Zhong et al., 2024) or entire nations (Khan et al., 2022).

Furthermore, sustainability studies do not focus only on economic considerations, but integrate resilience with the so-called triple bottom line of sustainability—economy, environment, and society—intending that economic recovery after a shock does not come at the expense of ecological degradation or social injustice (Aguñaga et al., 2018; Negri et al., 2021). This increases the complexity of establishing effective policies for resilience, as there are usually tradeoffs between increasing performance across the three dimensions of the triple-bottom line (Adaloudis & Bonnin Roca, 2021; Cavender-Bares et al., 2015). In particular, growth-driven economies might be reluctant to sacrifice short-term economic competitiveness to build long term resilience.

Within the sustainability literature, resilience is often framed around four interrelated concepts: adaptability, transformability, redundancy, and diversity.

Adaptability and transformability are strongly connected in practice (Daniele et al., 2022).

Adaptability is the capacity of a system to adjust its internal processes to respond to changing external conditions, while remaining in the same path (Zank et al., 2019). Achieving adaptability requires the existence of flexible institutions that can swiftly change strategies and reallocate resources, and to pay attention to potential interdependencies across government bodies in the design of critical infrastructure (Gim & Miller, 2022). Transformability, in contrast, refers to a system's ability to redefine itself – creating a new regime or pathway following disruption (Folke et al., 2010). Achieving transformation requires the coordination of top-down and bottom-up forces, which is often enabled by decentralized governance structure (Haddad et al., 2022).

Likewise, redundancy and diversity are also interrelated. Redundancy refers to having backup systems, such as local food reserves, or decentralized energy grids, which can keep operating when there is a problem in one of the nodes of the network (Davis et al., 2021; Hanna & Marqusee, 2022). However, redundancy can conflict with economic efficiency, as it requires higher initial investments and often foregoes scale economies (Markolf et al., 2022). Diversity, meanwhile, implies that systems with varied industrial sectors, income sources, or ecological components, are more resilient than those relying on a narrow specialization. This specialization increases exposure to external dependencies, particularly in globally interconnected systems (Nyström et al., 2019). The ecological analogy is clear: economic monocultures face similar vulnerabilities to their biological counterparts (Grêt-Regamey et al., 2019).

From a policy perspective, one of the key challenges in applying the sustainability-based view of resilience is the lack of robust, standardized metrics for evaluating success. Given the generality of the resilience principles, the appropriate metrics to use are highly dependent on the context. While scholars have developed extensive lists of indicators for particular cases like local disaster resilience (Tariq et al., 2021), urban resilience (Osei-Kyei et al., 2023), social resilience (Champlin et al., 2023), there is no consensus on core indicators or methods. This limits comparability across cases and makes it difficult to evaluate policy effectiveness. Furthermore, evidence remains largely qualitative, with few causal studies establishing a clear link between resilience policies and long-term sustainability outcomes (Jones et al., 2021).

Resilience from a corporate management perspective

In the management perspective, the objective of resilience is often more tangible than for the other two streams: the survival of the firm, and the return to the same, or better, levels of financial performance after recovering from a shock. The concept of firms' resilience is tightly connected to supply chain resilience, as it is understood that a company cannot operate in isolation, and its performance depends on the performance of upstream and downstream supply chain actors (Ambulkar et al., 2015; Novak et al., 2021). Theoretically speaking, most studies build upon the resource-based view of the firm (Do et al., 2022; Iftikhar et al., 2021). According to this theory, firms can gain a competitive advantage by integrating strategic resources, such as human capital and technology, to develop internal capabilities which determine the effectiveness of firms' actions (Barney, 1991; Brandon-Jones et al., 2014). Heterogeneity in resources and capabilities across firms in a region, or sector, may explain why some firms survive external shocks, while others do not (Ferreira & Fernandes, 2017).

The vast majority of corporate studies are centered around the firm, and the connection with the policy field is absent. Despite the fact that management scholars recognize that firms' resilience depend on institutions external to the firm, and that governments may play a key role during major disruptions (Azadegan & Dooley, 2021; Gereffi et al., 2022), most studies simply ignore the policy component. While this might be reasonable in studies analysing companies within a single region or country, which are all subject to the same policies and regulations, it is an important shortcoming when dealing with international networks, as there might be critical differences across countries in topics such as data privacy (Ogbuke et al., 2022), civil rights (Berliner et al., 2015), environmental protection standards (Thorlakson et al., 2018), or trade protectionism (Handley et al., 2020).

Unlike research in economics and environmental studies, much of the corporate literature has focused on a more pragmatic approach to the development of metrics and strategies which allow firms to actively predict and respond to disruptions. Over the years, scholars have developed comprehensive lists of desirable resilience capabilities and metrics (Stadtfeld & Gruchmann, 2023). While lists of capabilities differ slightly across authors, they typically revolve around three large pillars: effective information management and resource integration, strengthening collaboration across supply chain actors, and increasing operational flexibility (Han et al., 2020; Akhtar et al., 2024). These pillars are largely interconnected. Therefore, to have a noticeable effect on resilience, it is not enough that a focal company implements those changes, but they need to happen across the entire supply chain (Adobor, 2019; Novak et al., 2021).

In developing resilience strategies, management scholars emphasize the relevance of timing in firms' actions. From a temporal perspective, scholars distinguish four different phases (Han et al., 2020; Scholten et al., 2019): readiness, response, recovery, and renewal. Readiness refers to the ability to face a disruption based on a set of proactive actions taken before the disruption happens. To increase readiness, organizations should pre-emptively evaluate and interpret possible supply chain risks, while preparing contingency plans to secure their operations in case of need (Ali et al., 2017). Response refers to the ability to react to a disruption immediately after it happens. The objective in this stage should be to minimize financial losses and recovery time (Chowdhury & Quaddus, 2016). Recovery is the ability to restore supply chain operations after the disruption, which may require changing firms' operations to adapt to the new situation (Ivanov, 2024). Renewal goes beyond recovery and entails obtaining a higher level of resilience after having learned from the experience of a disruption (Hohenstein et al., 2015).

Despite the general disconnect between the management and policy literatures, in the last five years numerous scholars have highlighted the potential benefits of conducting research at the intersection of both fields (Anderson et al., 2023; Helper et al., 2021; Hughes et al., 2025). However, these voices also recognize that the relationship between firms' operations and policy is complex and bi-directional. On one hand, public policies can alter the resilience of firms, for instance by modifying the available

resources to them, and imposing restrictions on their operational flexibility. On the other hand, firms' capabilities and overall resilience may alter the need for, and effectiveness of, public policy responses to an external shock.

Implications of differences across fields for policymaking

Designing policies to build a resilient socioeconomic system requires a holistic approach that combines insights from economics, sustainability, and management. However, policymakers should be aware that, even though there is a degree of complementarity between academic fields, also some tensions exist in terms of the norms and the key definitions used.

These differences may lead to semantic confusion, and in the worst case, to counterproductive policies. While *adaptation* in the sustainability literature refers to a non-transformative response to a shock, in economics *adaptive resilience* implies a shift beyond the previous status quo to reduce the impact of future events. Transformability in sustainability is therefore more closely related to the concept of renewal in the management literature, where strategic reorganization occurs within the same structural boundaries (Herbane, 2019). However, even renewal often implies a significantly lower degree of change than transformation. An oil company, for instance, may go through a renewal process to adapt to geopolitical tensions which cause volatility in oil prices, but it is unlikely it will transform their core activity from oil to renewable energy. This raises a fundamental question: is a major shock a necessary condition for transformation – as suggested by the concept of creative destruction – and, if so, what costs is society willing to bear to enable such change?

Practitioners should also be aware of the differences in the underlying assumptions and objectives of each field. Resilience studies focus, at their core, on the self-preservation of the system they study. However, the system object of investigation differs substantially across fields. In economics, it refers to the existing institutional framework, industrial structures, and wealth. In management, the preservation of the firm. In ecology and sustainability studies, the environment and societal welfare. Unfortunately, it is likely that policies which strongly push for a higher resilience from a sustainability perspective, such as commitments to circular economy (Çetin & Kirchherr, 2025), may lower the resilience of other systems. For instance, diversity and redundancy are key principles of resilience across fields. However, in energy policy that may imply not only to invest in different types of renewable energies, but also to keep a portion of the economy running on fossil fuels. In trade policy, it may imply establishing trade agreements with parties which do not fully respect the own country's standards of social sustainability, especially in some sectors, such as the mining of rare earths, where supply is heavily limited (Nygaard, 2023).

Likewise, all three fields recognize that resilience consists of both a proactive and a reactive component, but policy can rarely improve both at the same time. The proactive component, often termed inherent resilience or readiness, depends on existing levels of redundancy and diversity within a socioeconomic structure. The reactive component, or adaptive resilience, hinges on the flexibility of institutions and their capacity to reallocate resources when disruptions occur. Striking the right balance between proactive and reactive resilience inherently requires making compromises between short-term efficiency and long-term robustness. Ideally, long-term policies should be in place as a proactive component, and allow for enough flexibility to implement changes when a shock occurs. From a company perspective, this may require costly investments in technological infrastructure, process redundancies, and, generally speaking, an allocation of resources which is suboptimal for daily business operations. Such investments not only challenge profit-maximizing strategies but may also clash with environmental principles that prioritize minimizing energy and resource consumption.

These tensions raise the question: **what is resilience-oriented policy?** Ideally, good resilience-oriented policies should 1) be cross-cutting across industrial sectors, to embrace the principles of diversity and redundancy; 2) combine short-term and long-term measures, to take into consideration the proactive and reactive components of resilience; and 3) focus on building networks with relevant societal stakeholders to ensure an equitable response to, and recovery from, potential disruptions.

In practice, given the different resilience traditions across fields, it is possible that different ministries or departments within the same government, may use resilience in a different manner, leading to semantic drift and arising confusion among both policymakers and citizens. In practice, most existing policy frameworks which tackle resilience explicitly, such as the European RRF or the American NDRF, focus almost exclusively on short-term economic recovery, neglecting opportunities for long-term transformation. The resilience dashboards developed by the Joint Research Center from the European Commission recognize four dimensions: social and economic, environmental, digital, and geopolitical. However, they do not delve into the interrelations among the four dimensions, which oversimplifies the complex interrelationships between economic actors and has very limited explanatory power. Consequently, their usefulness in helping design and evaluate consistent resilience policies is limited.

Furthermore, a persistent problem across disciplines is the development of *ex-ante* metrics to assess resilience, which hinders the evaluation of resilience-oriented policies. Macroeconomic indicators can offer a snapshot of economic health, but lack the granularity needed to design targeted resilience policies. Firm-level indicators about operational efficiency, while detailed, have limited relevance for broader governance. From a sustainability perspective, standardized measures for system transformability are lacking, and most existing frameworks apply only to narrow use cases. In addition, resilience poses an additional challenge for analysts akin to the Lucas critique: How reliable is data collected during normal operations, to assess how ready we are to face a Black Swan event? During a large shock, such as the recent pandemic, production and inventory levels may fluctuate dramatically across sectors (Fisher Ke et al., 2022), and critical suppliers may either shut down or oversupply, causing stark cascading effects (Scarpin et al., 2022). This added volatility can render many existing models inapplicable during or immediately after a disruption. To make better decisions, policymakers need models which accommodate to the size of their polity (supranational, national, regional, local), and that take into consideration the dynamic relationships among the dimensions of the triple-bottom line.

A research agenda for policy-oriented resilience studies

In light of the limitations of the three resilience perspectives we discussed, and the broader complexity of resilience as a policy goal, we strongly believe that the discourse on resilience would benefit from greater spatiotemporal granularity, which can only be achieved by integrating insights from different scholarly fields. Some disruptions—such as pandemics or financial crises—are global in nature, while others, such as geopolitical conflicts, are spatially localized. Similarly, shocks differ in duration. Short-lived disruptions (e.g., natural disasters) may require recovery-focused adaptation, to allow society to go back to normal as quickly as possible, and to avoid the negative effects of similar disruptions in the future; while protracted disruptions, such as long-lasting geopolitical conflicts, demand structural adjustment or even transformation to cut down inviable economic activities, and find new opportunities for prosperity. Current literature often fails to clarify how generalizable resilience frameworks are across these different contexts. Future research should explicitly differentiate resilience strategies according to disruption type, scope, and timeline, and explore how adaptive policies evolve under conditions of shifting uncertainty.

Understanding resilience, and providing effective policy responses, requires the development of multi-level models which take into consideration interdependencies among social, environmental, and

economic systems (see Figure 1). In this respect, the complementarities between the three academic fields suggest opportunities for integration. For instance, economic models could incorporate management-derived metrics of organizational agility and flexibility to better simulate long-term macroeconomic stability under shocks, as evidenced by the post-COVID recovery of global trade networks (Ocicka et al., 2022). Conversely, management research might integrate sustainability frameworks like the planetary boundaries (Mulligan et al., 2025; Myers et al., 2025) concept to evaluate short-term corporate strategies not only for profitability but also for their contributions to ecological thresholds and social equity, thereby addressing gaps in traditional risk assessment tools. Sustainability studies, which often focus on the community level, can act as a bridge between the two, and help develop hybrid indicators jointly with societal stakeholders, such as resilience indices that blend GDP growth projections with biodiversity loss (Kennedy et al., 2023) and social welfare metrics (Oliveira et al., 2021).

Qualitatively, multi-level embedded case studies can help developing theory and hypotheses about the relationships between variables across levels (Kühl et al., 2022; Øyri & Wiig, 2022). Quantitatively, large-scale simulation-based stress tests can help identify the elements of a system which are more likely to fail, but existing models are limited in scope and fail to model the interdependencies between systems (European Parliament, 2023; Linkov et al., 2022). To overcome the limitation of economic models, and quantify complex relationships such as nonlinearities, delays and feedback loops, which standard economic models cannot handle, a potential solution is the use of system dynamics models (Anderson et al., 2023). System dynamics models present several characteristics which can help overcome some of the limitations of standard economic models (Sterman, 2002). They allow users to analyze the influence of behavioral drivers and organizational routines on the desired economic, social, and environmental outcomes (Guzzo et al., 2024). In addition, they can be used to model interdependencies between variables at the micro-, meso-, and macro- levels (Walrave & Raven, 2016).

Building large-scale models which can be used for policymaking will require tackling another of the shortcomings of existing work, which is the lack of explicit treatment of trade-offs between the three dimensions of the triple bottom line: economic, environmental, and social. Much of the existing literature tends to privilege one dimension—typically economic or environmental—while neglecting others, although policies differ largely depending on how tradeoffs between dimensions are established (Ssekajja, 2024). In particular, the social dimension is often overlooked. We acknowledge the difficulty in quantifying environmental or social outcomes, and recognize that societies will differ in how they prioritize these dimensions.

Figure 1 Resilience-oriented policymaking requires the integration of multiple data sources into complex simulation models

There will never exist a universal one-size-fits-all solution. Instead, models need to be adaptable to support differences in normative framing across governments. To calibrate such models for each individual policymaker, researchers may rely on multi-criteria decision making tools (Bose et al., 1997; Kumar et al., 2017). Expert elicitation (van Valkenhoef & Tervonen, 2016) and Delphi methods can be used to understand individual preferences, estimate probability distributions for variables for which data is scarce, and help policymakers understand the range of possible outcomes to make better-informed decisions. A recent study used expert elicitation, for instance, to reveal ‘hidden’ interactions among seven Earth system processes which affect sustainable food production (Chrysafi et al., 2022). Likewise, the techniques could be used to assess how the variables at the micro-, meso-, and macro-levels of resilience interact. When using these methods, researchers should include a representative sample of all relevant stakeholders; take measures to mitigate the influence of individual biases; and conduct individual exercises before starting group deliberations (Morgan, 2014).

Running and validating those models requires the existence of large databases with up-to-date, high-quality data. However, in our own conversations with members of the European Commission, policymakers have highlighted the lack of data infrastructure and the low quality of existing data as a key challenge to running their models. To solve this problem, we also see an emerging opportunity which deserves further research.

In recent years, the European Union has introduced major legislative efforts—including the Critical Raw Materials Act, the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive, and the European Chips Act—which aim to govern global supply chains, mitigate systemic risks, and enhance resilience by fostering coordination between public and private actors. The scholarly discussion around these regulations has mostly highlighted the significant regulatory burdens these frameworks impose, particularly the requirement for companies to collect and report extensive operational data to national or EU authorities (Gustafsson et al., 2023; Kolev-Schaefer & Neligan, 2024). However, scholars have neglected that the vast amount of data collected under these regulatory efforts could, if properly processed, be fed to simulation models to perform stress tests of the socio-ecological-economic system (Ivanov & Dolgui, 2022). In particular, it could help improve our understanding of trade interdependencies and potential failure points in existing supply chains, the regional distribution of firms sensitive to specific disruptions, the operational flexibility of different industrial sectors, and broader patterns of social sustainability practices across the globe. The data collected via these regulatory efforts should be considerably richer than standard economic, environmental, and social indicators typically used in policymaking. In the best case, it could help provide near-real-time insights into system vulnerability and adaptive capacity. As a starting point, we encourage research into how to design public data infrastructures to better support resilience-oriented decision-making; and how these data streams could be harnessed using artificial intelligence methods, while respecting privacy and confidentiality norms.

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